

Gender Differences in Investment Behavior and Implications for Policy; Kenya Capital Markets Authority

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Abstract:

A number of researches had shown that investment choice was affected by various demographic factors. An increasing number of financial studies conclude that women invest their asset portfolios more conservatively than their male counterparts. The existence of these gender differences raises important questions for public policy. Main objective the research study was analyze the gender differences in investment behavior among employees of the Kenya Capital Markets Authority. Specifically, the research study sought to ascertain whether those differences exist, establish the relationship between gender differences in income levels and investment decisions and determine the relationship between gender difference in literacy levels and investment decisions. The overconfidence theory postulates that people generally rate themselves above average in their abilities and hence overestimate their precision of knowledge relative to others. They therefore believe that they can consistently beat the market. While, the Prospect Theory states that individuals value gains and losses differently in uncertain situations (that women underweight uncertain outcomes as compared to outcomes that can be obtained with certainty, and thus become risk averse for potential gains and risk seeker for possible losses). To achieve the objective, both descriptive as the primary information data source and inferential with a targeted of about 149 employees of the Capital Markets Authority who were assumed to have had similar exposures and hence expected to behave rationally irrespective of the demographic factors. A semi- structured questionnaire was prepared to collect the required information from the respondents while data analysis was done using descriptive statistics and inferential statistics such as, cross tabulations, Chi-square, Phi and Cramers V-test. The research study findings were evidenced that there was no difference in investment patterns in financial assets attributable to gender. Both gender considered a balance between risk and return when making investment decisions, but women are more inclined to capital preservation compared to men who prefer higher returns. there exists a weak negative relationship between Gender of the respondent and the percentage of the income invested. This was inconsistent with reviewed literature which indicated that men invest a higher percentage of their income compared to women from the data analyzed we observed that single women in the same income band invested higher percentage of their income. Similarly, it was evidenced that older married women invest more than their male counterparts. It further, revealed that there existed a positive weak relationship between the percentage of income invested in financial assets and the gender of the respondent. This implied that investors invest more in other assets compared to financial assets. However, on the investment literacy level, it was evidenced that more men than women relied on personal research and judgment to make investment decisions while most women relied on salespeople and intermediaries. The major research study findings evidenced that the respondents prefer more stable investments regardless of the gender as indicated by the high response (93.7%) preference for capital preservation. The research study recommends that targeted strategies by CMA including marketing, personalized services and investor protection measures as well as ensuring gender disaggregated data is maintained for all aspects of the capital markets to facilitate informed policy decisions. Furthermore, the Authority should strengthen the roll-out of financial education and literacy programmes to create awareness. Thus that it was evidenced that Financial literacy should commence at a young age and mainstream in the Kenya education system Curriculum with Market intermediaries needed to devise and apply gender-differentiated strategies appropriate for each gender in their investment advisory work.

Key words: Gender Differences, Investment Behavior, Implications of Policy; Kenya, and Capital Markets Authority.

INTRODUCTION

Investors perform investment analysis by making use of fundamental analysis, technical analysis and judgment. Investment decisions are often supported by decision tools (Iyer & Bhaskar, 2012). However, it is assumed that information structure as well as market factors systematically influence individuals' investment decisions and market outcomes (Clark- Murphy & Soutar, 2013). Iyer & Bhaskar (2012) postulate that investor market behavior derives from psychological principles of decision making in explaining why investors undertake investment.

While making investment decisions, investors, whether informed practically or technically about the industry of interest, still portray some aspects of behavioral irrationality of the fear of future loss. This different behavior by individual investors is caused by various factors which compromise the investor rationality. However, it is generally assumed that investment decisions are a function of several factors like market characteristics and individual risk profiles, in addition to accounting information (Clark-Murphy & Soutar, 2013). The disposition error shows that, irrespective of accounting information, investors are influenced by sunk cost considerations and asymmetrical risk preferences for gain or loss situations (Iyer & Bhaskar, 2012).

Globally, gender differences in many areas including education, income, and wealth have narrowed but in terms of long-term financial security there still exist disparities (Lemaster & Strough, 2013). Researchers and financial practitioners alike maintain that women invest their financial resources more conservatively and generally accept less financial risk than men (Lemaster & Strough, 2013). Researchers have also found out that women don't invest as much as men do. Additionally, women don't invest as early as men do, either (Sallie Krawcheck 2018, and Jennifer Barrett 2019). The disparity in long-term financial security between men and women is more pronounced in developing countries compared to developed countries where gender equity across many spheres has not been realized.

Some of the psychological factors that affect investment decisions include emotional sentiments. Investors are influenced by how investment problems are presented to them. They often make different choices pertaining to similar scenarios dependent on how the problem has been framed. Individuals considering investing usually conduct environment scanning for purposes of making knowledgeable investment decisions (Roszkowski & Grable, 2010; Bhushan & Medury, 2013). Individuals also tend to portray different behaviors while investing given the risk and the expected returns generated from such investments. Potential investors in developed countries differ significantly in various aspects, like beliefs, lifestyles, behaviors, habits and personal characteristics.

In a study of the relationship between an individual's demographic factors and investment behavior in India, demographic factors were found to insignificantly influence the kind of investment selected (Kesavan et al (2012). In Chitra & Sreedevi (2011) personality traits of investors were significant in influencing choice of investment method. Bayyurt et al (2013) in contrast noted that, while men investors prefer common stocks and real estate investment, women investors are more risk averse and would rather invest in funds, and time deposit. Willows (2012) posits that trading frequency lowers investors' return, and that men trade more than women, while in terms of a risk adjusted basis, women earn higher returns than men.

In Kenya, there have been conscious efforts to enhance financial inclusion of women including promoting digital finance, equalization funds such as Women Enterprise Fund aimed at enhancing women access to credit and financing facilities for purposes of investment. This is in addition to affirmative action in procurement among others. Similarly, a number of Micro-Finance Institutions (MFIs) over the years have been targeting women entrepreneurs by not only offering financial support but also training programs aimed at promoting investment opportunities for women. Despite the significant improvement in access to finance over the years, financial inclusion gaps persist as measured by sex, age, education, residence, income, livelihood and wealth quantiles (Finaccess Survey 2019). Access to finance by males is higher than that for females in the population

with formal inclusion at 80 percent for females compared to 86 for males which is above the 82.9 national average.

Given the above facts the research study sought to investigate whether there are any significant gender differences in investment behavior amongst employees of the capital markets Authority and the factors behind those differences including satisfaction levels with different investment options, income levels and financial literacy. This study was underpinned by two theories, the overconfidence theory and the Prospect Theory. The overconfidence theory postulates that people generally rate themselves above average in their abilities and hence overestimate their precision of knowledge relative to others. They therefore believe that they can consistently beat the market. Women have a lower inclination towards overconfidence in investment decisions and therefore display an increased risk aversion compared with men, while men are more prone to overconfidence than women, especially in male-dominated fields such as finance (Koech & Mukoba, 2016). It was also found that as knowledge increases men become more risk averse, while women take up more risk thus narrowing the confidence gap. On the other hand, the Prospect Theory states that individuals value gains and losses differently in uncertain situations. The theory states that women underweight uncertain outcomes as compared to outcomes that can be obtained with certainty, and thus become risk averse for potential gains and risk seeker for possible losses.

Statement of the Problem of research study

According to the Women in Financial Services 2020 report, two thirds of global consumer spending is controlled by women, while forty percent of total global wealth is now held by women. Additionally, women are twenty-five percent less confident in their financial acumen compared to men. On the contrary, women in retirement have lower balances than men and are more likely to be in poverty. Despite the growing role of women in financial services and their increasing role as consumers their needs are consistently not being met.

Over the years, financial institutions have continued to employ individual demographics such as gender in classifying investors into risk appetite clusters. Such risk tolerance categorization forms the foundation for creating investment management standards, controlling purchases and sales of investments, and managing overall client resources (Gostkowski & Grable, 2010). Although this information could be important, it has been observed that relying on a set of demographic factors for investors with different exposure levels to classify and determine investor risk tolerance can be misleading and might not necessarily improve investment outcome.

Gender differences in risk tolerance have critical implications for women. Variations in risk preferences between men and women may lead to differences in portfolio allocations and consequently wealth inequality (Yao, Sharpe, & Wang, 2011). For instance, women with lower levels of risk tolerance might not be prepared adequately for retirement given their longevity and individual responsibility placed on retirement savings today. Financial advisers note that women hold portfolios that are more conservative and yield lower returns (Fisher, & Yao 2017) Conservative investments can lead to lower levels of wealth accumulation that contribute to the gender gap in wealth.

In addition, there is general consensus among researchers and investment managers that more research concerning the efficacy of certain demographics in categorizing someone into a risk tolerance cluster is required (Roszkowski & Grable, 2010; Lemaster & Strough, 2013). Developing an approach that looks at demographic factors for groups with similar exposure to not only differentiate investors among levels of investor risk tolerance and also classify individuals into risk categories could help improve investment outcomes. This research therefore sought to establish the gender differences in investment behavior among employees assumed to have relatively similar exposure and expected to behave rationally. Specifically, the study sought to examine whether gender differences in investing decisions exist; establish the relationship in gender difference to

satisfaction levels towards various investment instruments and determine the relationship in gender difference and investment literacy levels.

Research Objectives, Hypothesis and Conceptual Model

General Objective

The main objective of the research study was to analyze the existence of gender differences in investment behavior among employees of the Capital Markets Authority (CMA).

Specific Objectives

- i. Examine the gender differences in investment behavior among CMA employees
- ii. Examine the relationship between gender differences in income levels and investment decisions.
- iii. Determine the relationship between gender differences in literacy levels and investment decisions.

Research Questions

- i. Why gender differences in investment behavior among CMA employees?
- ii. Whether there is a relationship between gender differences in income levels and investment decisions?
- iii. Whether existence of a relationship between gender differences and investment literacy levels?

Assumptions

- i. The respondents are active savers and therefore have investable money at their disposal.
- ii. The respondents are aware about the possible investment options at their disposal.
- iii. The respondents are individuals capable of making decisions at an individual personal level.

Justification of the research study

In a competitive world, firms are shifting their approaches to extend their reference to the client.

While many factors result in greater client centricity, gender is a crucial element. Financial Services Study 2020 report estimates that financial services firms are losing a minimum of a USD\$700 billion revenue opportunity every year by not fully meeting the requirements of female customers. A variety of research has shown that investment choice is driven by various demographic factors. An increasing number of economic studies conclude that females invest their asset portfolios more conservatively than their male counterparts. Financial services firms have to understand the needs of women as customers and make propositions that meet these needs. The innovative solutions which will result from taking a gender-lens perspective will not only benefit women, but all customers. Against this background, this study sought to investigate the gender differences in investment behavior among employees of the Capital Markets Authority.

Significance of the research study

Women are perceived to be more conservative while investing and if determined to be so should be offered such financial products which benefit them in terms of risk and return characteristics. For this the developers and marketers of financial products should understand the gender differences in investment behavior of people. Against this backdrop, the current study is an attempt to analyze the gender differences in investment behavior among employees of the Capital Markets Authority. The findings of this study contribute to existing literature on gender differences in investment behavior and inform appropriate policy interventions such as legislations and tax considerations aimed at supporting greater market efficiency. To investment advisers, the study provides a better understanding of gender differences in investment behavior and hence devise appropriate portfolios and strategies for their clients.

Scope of the research study

This study focused on the pattern of investment of the employees of the Capital Markets Authority, determining whether there are any gender differences in investment choices, satisfaction levels and literacy levels. It is helpful in identifying the better investment options in the market for the different groups and inform policy considerations for incentivizing greater investment by women.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Prospect Theory or Loss-aversion theory

The Prospect Theory is also known as the loss-aversion theory. Since its formulation by Kahneman and Tversky in 1979, Prospect Theory is a theory of decision making under conditions of risk. In other words, the theory is best known for its hypothesis that individuals are risk averse when it comes to gains and risk acceptant when it comes to losses (Jack Levy 1992). Further, this theory describes how people make decisions when presented with alternatives that involve risk, probability and uncertainty.

Individuals give more regard to losses as compared to gains. As such, they therefore make choices in terms of deviations from a reference point (Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). The reference point is usually the status quo. Generally, people treat gains and losses differently. For example, when it comes to losses versus gains, people tend to remember losses more than gains. Put another way, they tend to remember more of the losses they suffer than the gains they made however big or large they were. This phenomenon of loss aversion implies that people prefer to retain the status quo over a 50/50 chance for positive and negative alternatives. It also implies that people value what they have more than "comparable" things they do not have.

Several studies have shown that individuals overweight outcomes which are certain relative to outcomes which are merely probable-the certainty effect (Allais, 1979; Kahneman & Tversky, 1979). In keeping with the Prospect Theory, even with an equal probability and equal outcome, investors tend to prefer avoiding loss than securing gains. Confronted with the opportunity of selecting between two equal probabilities, most investors would prefer to retain the wealth that they already have instead of taking the risk of extending their current wealth. People are usually averse to the chance of losing, such that they would rather avoid a loss instead of take a risk to create equal gain or sometimes even more gain.

The process of making these choices is in two phases. The first phase is the editing phase which involves the identification of the possible outcomes or consequences and the values and probabilities associated with each of the alternatives. The second phase is the evaluation phase which entails the evaluation of the prospects of either loss or gain. Once the evaluation is done, the best alternative is chosen.

Overconfidence theory

Overconfidence bias is one of many cognitive errors or biases discussed in behavioral finance. In the behavioral psychology literature, such as in Yates (1990); and Campbell et al. (2004), people who presume themselves to have more abilities than they actually retain, and who make decisions based on that presumption, are described as being overconfident. Glaser and Waber (2007) presented three manifestations of overconfidence: miscalibration, underestimation of volatility, and the "above average" effect. According to Glaser and Waber (2007), miscalibration is the difference between the accuracy and the probability assigned in any decision-making process. For instance, when asked to make a forecast without being precise but estimating within a certain confidence interval, people usually are less accurate. In a related study, De Bondt (1998) asked 46 stock market investors to predict stock prices and forecast risks in USA stock market. The results confirm that there is a miscalibration in the stock market since investors were asked to place 90% confidence intervals on their

predictions. In another word, they have found that most investors failed to specify a range of expected future stock prices. Glaser et al. (2013) obtained similar findings for student and professional stock traders.

Some studies focus on the volatility estimates of investors. For example, Hilton (2001); and Andersen et al. (2004) asked investors to each provide confidence intervals for the return or price of a stock in the future. These studies conclude that investors tend to provide intervals that are too tight and therefore deviate from the possibilities of a correct guesses; they underestimate historical volatilities.

A third form of overconfidence is the belief that one is better than the average person. This is called the “above average” effect. Studies by Beer and Hughes (2010); Sharot (2011); and ChamorroPremuzic and Furnham (2014) have confirmed the existence of this effect. Many researchers have concluded that the above average effect is nearly universal. Investors who attribute past success to their skill and past failure to bad luck are likely to be overconfident. An investor who is overconfident will want to utilize his perceived superior ability to obtain large returns. Overconfidence makes men comfortable with risk and drives them to take unnecessary and unjustifiable risk, resulting in wrong decisions. Studies have shown that one side effect of overconfidence is excessive trading. Barber and Odean (2001) showed that males earn lower net returns (after transaction costs) than females because they are more overconfident and hence they trade more aggressively, incurring higher transaction costs. They found that men trade 45% more than women and end up reducing their net returns by 2.65% a year as compared to 1.72% for women.

Gender lens investing

The role of gender in investment decisions is a debatable issue. Patty Alleman et al (USAID, 2015) defined gender lens investing as the intentional integration of a gender analysis into financial analysis to make better investment decisions. Gender analysis has been defined as a systematic analytical process used to identify, understand, and describe gender differences and the relevance of gender roles and power dynamics in a specific context.

Evidence for gender differences in risk taking

Several past studies have recognized that women are more risk averse compared to men (Dohmen et al., 2011). Similarly, key findings from previous studies conclude that women hold lower proportions of risky assets (Halko et al., 2012), they are more risk averse (Dohmen et al., 2011) and also less overconfident. Marinelli, N, et al (2016) in their study, found that the main difference found in the previous literature is the already acknowledged higher financial risk tolerance of men. However, more recent research suggest that these gaps tend to disappear when socio-demographic and economic characteristics between men and women, such as financial literacy, are considered. Hibbert et al., (2013) and Almenberg and Dreber (2015) work suggest that these gaps tend to disappear when socio-demographic and economic characteristics such as financial literacy are considered. Bannier and Neubert (2016) study further strengthen this finding by showing the significance of financial literacy (actual or perceived) in financial risk taking, with different degrees for men and women. The study by Marinelli, N, et al (2016) examined investment behavior by categorizing them in three dimensions: decision process, risk preferences and actual portfolios. Their key finding was that even after controlling for socio-demographic and economic variables, a “gender factor” is still responsible for men and women's differences in their investment behavior.

Halkoa, Kaustiab and Alan kocIn (2011) compared several measures of risk attitude using respondents that are familiar with financial risks (and from Finland, one of the most gender equal countries in the world) and found that a self-reported financial risk attitude is the strongest predictor of the proportion of wealth invested in stocks. They also found that women are more risk-averse compared to men. Their main contribution was that gender is still a strong predictor of risk taking in subjects with extensive personal and professional experience with financial matters. Gary Charnessa and Uri Gneezy (2011) assembled data from fifteen sets of experiments

with one simple underlying investment game and found a very consistent result that women appear to be more financially risk averse than men mainly because they invest less

Impact of demographic factors on investment decisions

Chavali and Mohanraj (2016) studied demographic variables like gender, age and occupation and personal financial risk tolerance and found that gender is the only demographic variable which has an impact on investment patterns. However, it is generally difficult to attribute the degree of financial risk taking to a single attribute; instead, scholars think a variety of characteristics influence it, including personality behaviors, perceived importance by the individual and age, Figner and Weber (2011).

A study by Pathak Sunita and Pathak Tanvi (2014) revealed that safety is the most preferred motive of investment while other factors are less preferred. It was also established that there is a significant difference for the choice of motives of investment for different gender and age groups. It was concluded based on Mann whitney and Kruskal Wallis test (ranking rather than raw values analysis) that motives of investment differ as demographic variable changes, hence there is a relationship between demographic variables (gender and age groups) and motives of doing investment.

Impact of behavioral factors on investors' financial decisions

Investment behaviors of men and women vary in several ways. Kappal and Rastogi (2020) asserted that individual investment behavior is affected by personality, gender difference, socio-economic environment, attitudes, myths and other demographic factors. Metawa N, et al (2017) observed that investor sentiment, overreaction and underreaction, overconfidence and herd behavior significantly affect investment decisions. Also, age, gender and the level of education have significant positive effects on investment decisions. Experience does not play a significant role in investment decisions, but as investors gain experience, they tend to overlook the emotional factors.

Wieland. A, (2012) finding was that gender differences in risk aversion are likely to occur in decisions under risk, where the probability of outcomes is known and objectively quantified and less likely to occur in decisions under uncertainty, where one must rely on their own, internal, subjective expectancies of the probabilities of outcomes. In decisions under risk, when subjective expectancies are accounted for, the gender difference in risk aversion disappears; while in decisions under uncertainty, no gender differences in risk aversion was observed.

The simplistic commonly held assumption that women are more risk averse than men was refuted. Most decisions faced on a day-to-day basis are those where the probability of the outcomes is unknown, decisions under uncertainty. In the three studies examined, gender differences in risk aversion in decisions involving uncertainty, when the participant must rely on their own internal subjective expectancies, there was no evidence found of gender differences in risk aversion in these decisions under uncertainty. The conclusion of this study was that the generally accepted conclusion that women are normally more risk averse than men should be revisited. The study by Marinelli. N, et al (2016) presents a new perspective which attributes differences in investment behaviors across gender types not to gender itself but rather to the socio-demographic and economic characteristics differences in our society related to gender. Past studies have largely analyzed a single characteristic connecting gender to investment behaviors, thus neglecting other important and unexplored factors of financial investment decision making. In this research we have also examined the financial literacy factor in investment decision making.

Conceptual framework

The diagram below shows the relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variables. The independent variables are income levels and financial literacy levels among the employees of CMA. The dependent variable is investment decisions assessed using the following parameters: taxation, rate of return,

policy and legal certainty, capital preservation, growth/capital gains, speculation and risk appetite. Gender is the moderating variable in the study.

Figure 2.1: Conceptual Framework

Source: odula (2022)

Research Gap

Most of the reviewed studies have not laid emphasis on financial literacy. This paper sought to measure this key variable by adding a question on financial literacy through collection of more detailed information on education levels and awareness and attitudes towards investment. The study also analyzed the age pattern, for both female and male respondents, with a view to supporting the view that the gender effect in risk attitude is at least partially biological.

The target population is largely homogenous, in terms of exposure to financial knowledge, hence the study targeted to establish the extent to which gender is a significant factor in investment decision making. This may help in reaching a conclusion as to whether financial advice can be a source of value addition in investment decision making. This may remotely help assess whether investing based on advice from market intermediaries may lead to more risk-taking behavior compared to investment by an uninformed individual.

The study was also designed to also establish whether gender, age, income or education (financial literacy) are determinants in investment behaviors. Although the studies in this area are inconclusive, and the outcome of this study is still limited by assumptions made, a call for further and targeted work is necessary to inform policy and regulatory action and reforms.

RESEARCH DESIGN AND METHODOLOGY

Research Design of the study

This study used an explanatory and or descriptive research design and the questionnaire method was adopted to collect primary information from the entire population. An Explanatory research approach is also commonly known as analytical research or correlation study and its main objective is to explain the relationships between

the variables under study (Chandran, 2004). The researchers deemed this design suitable since the study set out to establish the relationship between gender and investment decisions. The decision to use a mix of qualitative and quantitative data was selected due to its potential to improve the understanding of the investment behavior among men and women. It was used to aid in analysis of both numbers and explanations offered by the respondents. The data used information on ages, income levels, financial products chosen and reasons why certain choices were made.

Target Population of the research study

According to Kothari (2010), a population refers to an entire group of individuals, events or objects having common observable characteristics. The research targeted all the 149 employees of the Capital Markets Authority (CMA). The choice of this population was informed by the assumption that CMA staff understand financial products and there is a higher possibility that both women and men are investing in the financial markets. A key assumption of this study was that by examining the investment behaviors of this group, it would be possible to tease out the gender differences in demand, consideration and choices that influence investment in the financial products. This rationale is confirmed by Creswell (2009) who argues that the target population should have observable characteristics to which the study intends to generalize the result. Following these definitions, it is appropriate to conclude that the target population of interest is homogeneous.

Data Collection Procedures

According to Obwatho (2014), data collection instruments involve the techniques used to collect data from the respondents. Primary data was collected using a semi-structured, self-administered questionnaire that sought data on the profile of the respondents, on the correlation between income levels, gender and investment decisions, on relationship between financial literacy levels (awareness, knowledge and attitude) and investment decisions and to establish how laws, policies and risk appetite affect investment decisions.

Data Processing and Analysis

The data collected was sorted, cleaned and coded before analysis. Quantitative data was analyzed using inferential and descriptive statistics to establish the investment behavior for each gender. The study utilized the Pearson Correlation analysis in analyzing the strength of the relationship between the gender, level of income, the percentage of monthly income invested and percentage of income invested in financial assets. Characteristics of the data were also analyzed in terms of frequencies and summaries in a bid to gain insight on the study topic. Data was presented using graphs and charts for ease of comparison using frequencies, averages, mode and any other relevant tool available.

RESEARCH FINDINGS, DATA ANALYSIS PRESENTATION AND INTERPRETATION

Gender of the respondents

The study sought to establish the gender of the respondents being one of the independent variables. As illustrated by Table 4.1 the study established that gender balance was achieved in this study in the administration of the questionnaire whereby 50% male and 50% female filled in the questionnaire.

Table 4.1: Gender of the Respondent

Category	Frequency	Percent
Male	32	50.0
Female	32	50.0
Total	64	100.0

Source: odula (2022)

Marital Status

The study sought to find out the proportion of the respondents who were single and those that were married, this being one of the variables expected to affect investment behavior. As indicated by Figure 4.1, out of the 64 respondents 60.9% were married while 39.1% were single.

Figure 4 .1: Marital Status of the Respondents

Source: odula (2022)

Further to this, an analysis of the marital status according to gender as illustrated by Figure 4.2 indicates that most of the men that were interviewed (66.67%) were married whereas a majority of their female counterparts were single (76%).

Figure 4.2: Marital Status According to gender

Source: odula (2022)

Age distribution

The study sought to find out the age distribution among the respondents. As shown in Figure 4.3, most of the respondents were between the age of 30 and 45 years which accounted for 59.4% of the respondents. 23.4% of the respondents were between 45 to 60 years while 17.2% of the respondents were below 30 years.

Figure 4.3: Age distribution of the Respondents

Source: odula (2022)

A further analysis of the age distribution by gender as outlined by Figure 4.4 indicates that a majority of male respondents (66.67%) were between the age of 45 to 60 years while a majority of the female respondents (54.55%) were below 30 years of age. Female respondents also led in the age group between 20 to 45 years accounting for 55.26% while their male counterparts accounted for 44.74%.

Figure 4.4: Age Distribution by gender

Source: odula (2022)

Correlation between Income Levels, Gender and Investment Decisions

Income Distribution

According to Figure 4.5, 35.90% of the respondents were earning more than KES 300,000; 25% were earning between KES 200,000 and 300,000; 20.3% were earning between KES 100,000 while 18.8% were earning below KES 100,000.

Figure 4.5: Income Distribution

Source: odula (2022)

A further analysis of the income by gender as evidenced by Table 4.2 indicates that most of the male respondents earned KES 300,000 and above. This is in line with the findings on the age distribution whereby more males were in the age group between 45 to 60 years, a category that is mainly dominated by senior management of the Authority. On the other hand, most of the female respondents earned below KES 100,000 which is equally aligned with the findings on age whereby most of them were below 30 years thus implying that a majority of them are in the entry level whose income is low. In the KES 100,000 to KES 200,000 category the male respondents accounted for 53.85% while the KES 200,000-KES 300,000 category female respondents accounted for 56.25%.

Table 4.2: Income Distribution by Gender

Gender/Income	Below 100,000	KES 100,000-KES 200,000	KES 200,000-KES 300,000	KES 300,000 and Above
Male	16.67%	53.85%	43.75%	69.57%
Female	83.33%	46.15%	56.25%	30.43%

Source: odula (2022)

Financial Decision Making among the respondents

According to Table 4.3, 45.3% of the respondents make their money decisions; 43.8% consult partners; 3.1% that their parents are responsible while 6.3% of the respondents indicated that their spouses were responsible for the day-to-day money decisions.

Table 4.3: Decision Making among the respondents

Day to Day Decision Maker	Frequency	Percent
Self	29	45.3
Spouse/Partner	4	6.3
Parents	2	3.1
Me and my partner	28	43.8

Source: Odula (2022)

Proportion of money invested

According to Table 4.4, 46.9% of the respondents invest 5- 20% of their monthly income; 20.3% invest below 5%; 17.2% of the respondents invest 20 -40%; 4.7% of the respondents invest over 40% while 10.9% of the respondents do not invest.

Table 4.4: Percentage of Income Invested by Respondents

Percentage of Income Invested	Frequency	Percent
Nil	7	10.9
Below 5%	13	20.3
5%-20%	30	46.9
20%-40%	11	17.2
over 40%	3	4.7

Source: odula (2022)

The study utilized the Pearson Correlation analysis in analyzing the strength of the relationship between the gender, level of income, the percentage of monthly income invested, and percentage of income invested in financial assets. The Pearson correlation analysis was selected as it can be used when one of the variables is dichotomous (categorical) in our case the dichotomous variable was the gender which is one of the independent variables in the model. As highlighted by table 4.5 there is a moderate negative relationship between the Gender of the respondent and their Monthly gross income (-0.333) while there exists a weak negative relationship between Gender of the respondent and the percentage of the income invested. Additionally, the study revealed that there exists a positive weak relationship between the percentage of income invested in financial assets and the gender of the respondent. In terms of the monthly gross income, there exists a moderate positive (0.476) relationship between the percentage of income invested and a weak positive (0.278) relationship between the monthly Gross salary and the percentage of income invested in financial assets. This implies that investors invest more in other assets compared to financial assets. Some of the investment options included farming, real estate, gambling and land. This is despite the level of awareness of the capital markets products amongst CMA employees. This trend may be attributed to social-economic factors in Kenya where investments in real estate are highly appreciated regardless of the return.

From the data analyzed we observed that single women in the same income band invested higher percentage of their income. This may be explained by several other factors including a person's standard of living, expenditure patterns, social-cultural, among other factors that may impact on disposable income available for investment. Similarly, older married women invest more than their male counterparts. Additionally, the study revealed that there exists a positive weak relationship between the percentage of income invested in financial assets and gender. This is inconsistent with reviewed literature (Sallie Krawcheck 2018, and Jennifer Barrett 2019) which indicates that men invest a higher percentage of their income compared to women.

Table 4.5: Correlation Matrix Between Gender, Salary, Amount Invested and Amount invested in financial assets

Gender of the Monthly Gross Percentage of the Percentage to Variables Respondent Salary income
invested financial assets

Gender of the Respondent	1	-0.333	-0.253	0.076
Monthly Salary	Gross	-0.333	1	0.476
Percentage of the income invested		-0.253	0.476	1
Percentage of financial assets	to	0.076	0.278	0.471
				1

Source: odula (2022)

Relationship between Financial Literacy Levels (Awareness, Knowledge and Attitude) and Investment Decisions

As highlighted by table 4.6, 54.7% of the respondents had acquired their postgraduate qualification; 40.6% had a degree certificate; 3.1% of the respondents had Diploma while one respondent had a Secondary School certificate.

Table 4.6: Education Level of the Respondents

Secondary Certificate	1	1.6
Diploma	2	3.1
Degree Certificate	26	40.6
Postgraduate	35	54.7

Source: odula (2022)

Table 4.7 reveals that not all staff members are aware of the products that are regulated by the Authority which is the expectation. 21.90% indicated that they were not aware of Exchange Traded Funds while 12.5% were not aware of Collective Investment Schemes and Contracts for Difference.

Table 4.7: Literacy level on Financial Assets Among the Respondents

Financial Asset	Yes	No
Stocks	98.40%	1.60%
Corporate Bonds	92.20%	7.80%
Collective Investment Schemes	87.50%	12.50%
Contract for Difference	87.50%	12.50%
Treasury Bonds	95.30%	4.70%
Sacco Savings	100.00%	
ETFs	78.10%	21.90%
Insurance	95.30%	4.70%
Pension	98.40%	1.60%
Bank Loan	95.30%	4.70%

Source: odula (2022)

A further analysis as highlighted by Table 4.8 indicate the Phi and Cramer's V statistics value stood at 0.260 indicating a very weak association between the gender of the respondent and their level of education in investment decision making. This study infers that there exists no relationship between gender differences in literacy levels and investment decisions. Although this finding seems to contradict literature, Hibbert et al., (2013) and Almenberg and Dreber (2015), we note that the population of CMA is fairly homogenous hence the reason for the ubiquitous knowledge in investment spectrum.

Nevertheless, this finding may require to be corroborated since the population targeted in the study is relatively homogeneous with respect to literacy in the financial market. This finding is in line with recent research which suggest that gaps in making investment decisions between male and females tend to disappear when socio-demographic and economic characteristics between men and women, such as financial literacy, are considered. Past studies find that there is considerable evidence that financial literacy is correlated with wealth accumulation and portfolio decisions. However, financial literacy is a choice largely determined by education, accessibility to relevant information, past experiences and cost-benefit trade-offs.

Table 4.8: Association between Gender of the Respondent and their level of education

Association tests	Value	Approximate Significance
Phi	0.260	0.228
Cramer's V	0.260	0.228

Source: Research Findings (2021)

Sources of Information

In terms of the sources of information utilized by the respondents as they make investment decisions, Personal research and knowledge about a product was considered a leading source followed by Information from market intermediaries or salespersons offering the product while Advice from friends and relatives working in the financial sector or who hold such investments ranked third and Advice from spouse/partner or other family member ranked fourth.

Table 4.9: Identified Sources of Information that affect investment decisions among the respondents

Sources of Information influencing investment decisions	Very Important	Important	Neutral	Slightly Important	Not Important
Personal Research and Knowledge about a product	79.70%	20.30%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Information from market Intermediary/salesperson offering the product	31.30%	48.40%	14.10%	4.70%	1.60%
Advice from spouse/partner or other family member	21.90%	50.00%	15.60%	7.80%	4.70%
Advice from friends and relatives working in the financial sector or who hold such investments	17.20%	60.90%	14.10%	3.10%	4.70%

Note: 1 Very Important, 2 Important, 3: Neutral; 4: Slightly Important and 5: Not Important: Source: odula (2022)

A further analysis of the last trigger of investment among the respondents as outlined by Tables 4.10 and 4.11 indicates that 68.75% of the respondents considered products from various companies and analyzed the returns thereof with 26 being men and 18 women; 21.88% invest in only what they know and has been proven to avoid stress majority of whom were female (9 female, 5 male); 6.25% invested spontaneously (3 female and 1 male) while 3.13% followed the salespersons/colleague advice (all female). Remarkably, none of the respondent invested just because others were investing in certain products.

From the discussion we deduce that, males and females have different perspectives towards different information sources with males preferring to conduct self-research while females rely more on advice from investment advisers. This seems to contradict the overconfidence theory which attribute men to overconfidence when making investment decisions. However, the men in this study may be deemed to have a better exposure and understanding in the investment arena hence their approach to research prior to investing.

Table 4.10: Factors that influenced the respondent's last investment decisions

<i>How the respondents chose their last investment product</i>	<i>Percent</i>
I considered several products from various companies and analyzed and return before I chose one	68.75%
I only invested in what was offered what was offered to me by salesperson/colleague in the office and didn't look for any other alternative	3.13%
I only invest in what I know and has been proven and don't stress myself to consider other investments	21.88%
I invest only where everyone else is investing	0.00%
It was a spontaneous decision	6.25%

Source: odula (2022)

Table 4.11: A cross tabulation of Gender and How the last investment decision was made

How you last chose an investment product	<u>Total</u>					
	I considered several products from various companies and analyzed their risk and return before I chose one	I only invested in what was offered to me by the salesperson/colleague in the office and didn't look for any other alternative	I only invest in what I know and has been proven and don't stress myself to consider other investments	I invest where everyone else is investing	I invest where everyone else is investing	It was a spontaneous decision
Male	26	0	5	0	1	32
Female	18	2	9	0	3	32
Total	44	2	14	0	4	64

Source: odula (2022)

Investment Attitude

A keen analysis of the Investor risk attitudes indicates that 48.4% of the respondents have a moderate risk appetite; 20.3% of the respondents are somewhat conservative; 15.6% are somewhat aggressive; 9.4% are Very conservative while 6.3% are very aggressive in their investment decisions.

Table 4.12: Investment Attitude among the respondents

Investment Attitudes	Frequency	Percent
Very Conservative	6	9.4
Somewhat Conservative	13	20.3
Moderate	31	48.4
Somewhat aggressive	10	15.6
Very aggressive	4	6.3

Source: odula (2022)

Given that most of the variables in our questionnaire were measured using the ordinal and nominal levels of measurement the chi-square or Pearson's chi-square test was utilized to calculate the strength of the relationships between various variables. The following hypotheses were utilized in this analysis:

Null Hypothesis (HO): There is NO association between the variables

Alternative Hypothesis (HA): There is an association between the variables

The Phi and Cramer's V tests of association were used interchangeably in this analysis. The Phi is used to measure the strength of the association between two categorical variables with only two categories for example gender has two categories namely (Male and Female). On the other hand, the Cramer's V test is utilized when the variables have more than two categories.

Both the Phi and the Cramer's V statistics are 0.512 indicate that there is a moderate relationship between the gender and their investment attitude, thus confirming the literature reviewed (Halkoa, Kaustiab and Alan kocIn 2011).

Table 4.13: Association between Gender and Investment Attitude

Tests for Association	Value	Approximate Significance
Phi	0.512	0.002
Cramer's V	0.512	0.002

Source: odula (2022)

Relationship between laws, policies and risk appetite and investment decisions

An analysis of the factors that influence the respondents' decisions indicate that 87.5% of the respondents indicate that Taxation is important; 89.1% indicated that Policy and Legal Certainty is important; all the respondents indicated that Rate of return is important; 93.7% indicated that capital preservation is important; 98.4% highlighted that growth prospects/capital gains are important while 48.5% of them indicated that speculation is important.

Table 4.14: Factors Influencing Respondents' investment decisions

Factors	Influencing Respondents' investment decisions	Very important	Important	Neutral	Slightly Important	Not Important
Taxation		45.30%	42.20%	7.80%	0.00%	4.70%
Policy & Legal Certainty		54.70%	34.40%	10.90%	0.00%	0.00%
Rate of Return		85.90%	14.10%	0.00%	0.00%	0.00%
Capital Reservation		65.60%	28.10%	6.30%	0.00%	0.00%
Growth Prospects/Capital gains		78.10%	20.30%	0.00%	1.60%	0.00%
Speculation		9.40%	39.10%	29.70%	10.90%	10.90%

Source: *odula (2022)*

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

There was no significant difference found in investment patterns in financial assets attributable to gender. Both males and females consider a balance between risk and return when making investment decisions, but women are more inclined to capital preservation compared to men. This is an indicator of higher risk tolerance among the men compared to women.

The study also found that the majority of the respondents prefer more stable investments regardless of the gender. Additionally, that safety is the most preferred motive of investment while other factors are less preferred.

The study revealed that men do not necessarily invest a higher percentage of their income compared to women contrary to the reviewed literature.

The study found that there were no significant differences in awareness levels between males and females. It was established that more men than women relied on personal research and judgment to make investment decisions while most women relied on salespeople and market intermediaries.

Conclusion

Decision making for investments, usually preceded by savings, help an investor to earn more returns, satisfy all their needs and lead a better life. The weak relationship between gender and investment decisions implies that investment patterns are not generally dictated by gender. The degree of financial risk taking is attributed to several, other than one, demographic variables like gender, age, occupation and personal financial risk tolerance. The study has confirmed that financial literacy helps in availing choices to investors amidst the many options at their disposal.

Recommendations

Understanding the behavior of investors is of great value to CMA considering its twin mandate of market regulation and development. Since investors indicate their gender at the point of access to capital markets products, we posit that the availability of demographic characteristics (including age, gender, ethnicity, religion, income levels, education and marital status) is valuable in execution of targeted strategies including marketing, personalized services and investor protection.

Women rely more on investment advisers to make investment decisions whereas men depend more on personal research and knowledge prior to making investment decisions. Therefore, market intermediaries need to devise and apply gender-differentiated strategies appropriate for each gender in their investment advisory work.

There needs to be concerted efforts towards enhancing financial literacy across all genders as past studies provide evidence that financial literacy is a key factor in making investment decisions. The CMA should strengthen the roll-out of financial education and literacy programmes, alongside other financial sector players including Insurance Regulatory Authority (IRA), Central Bank of Kenya (CBK), Retirement Benefits Authority (RBA) and Sacco Societies Regulatory Authority (SASRA). Financial literacy should commence at a young age and hence discussions with the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development should be explored to include this in primary and secondary schools' curriculum.

The findings of this paper would help in stimulating a discussion in the understanding of the gender patterns in investment decision making which would help in the design of policies geared toward the growth of the Kenyan capital market.

The study was based on data collected from a relatively homogenous population. We recommend further work in this area of study by the research function of the CMA. This should target respondents drawn from a sample selected from a population with different demographic factors.

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